

A Study of the Effect of Addition of Ethanol on the Rate of Coagulation of Titanic Oxide Hydrosol

K. Chakravarti and B. N. Ghosh

Addition of ethanol to aqueous colloidal systems usually lowers the dielectric constant of the medium. In the case of titanic oxide hydrosol, mixed with KNO_3 , the gradual addition of EtOH promotes the sensitisation of the sol. Light-scattering method has been used to study this effect. A linear relation has been found between $\log(D/a)$ and $\log t$, where D , a , and t represent the dielectric constant of the medium, the activity of the added electrolyte, and the time to attain a particular turbidity of the sol, respectively.

The stability of a sol is very often influenced by the addition of non-electrolytes. This effect on stability may result from factors like dissociation of electrolytes, change of viscosity, dielectric constant of the medium, etc. Several authors¹⁻⁴ noticed a correlation between coagulation value and dielectric constant. Kratochvil *et al.*⁵ used AgBr sol to study the effect of coagulation in mixed solvents and showed that coagulation concentration decreased with a lowering of dielectric constant and with an increase in the concentration of stabilising Br^- ions. Ostwald *et al.*⁶ quoted measurements of Sorum⁷ in which the variation of coagulation value of NaCl for the coagulation of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol in 2 hours' time was investigated in presence of different amounts of ethanol and acetone. Some of the data of Sorum⁷ have also been used by us in this communication.

In the present investigation, the effect of gradual addition of ethanol on the rate of aggregation of TiO_2 hydrosol, mixed with KNO_3 , has been followed by measuring the intensity of scattered light at suitable intervals of time.

EXPERIMENTAL

Titanic oxide hydrosol was prepared by adding very pure TiCl_4 (E. Merck) from a hypodermic syringe to distilled water and shaking the mixture vigorously. The faintly white sol formed was dialysed for about 15 days, care being taken to check over-dialysis causing high viscosity and partial gelation of the sol. The sol was then allowed to age

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2. Tezak *et al.*, *Disc. Faraday Soc.* 1954, No. 18, 63.
3. Derjaguin and Landau, *Acta Physicochim., U S S R.*, 1941, **14**, 639.
4. Verwey and Overbeek, "Theory of Stability of Lyophobic Colloids", New York, 1948.
5. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1960, **64**, 1216.
6. *Kolloid Z.*, 1937, **81**, 49.
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8. Haydon, III. International Congress of Surface Activity, Cologne, 1960.

for 3 weeks. pH, percentage composition, and n_D^{25} of the sol were 3.76, 0.196 g./100ml, and 1.342 respectively.

The sol was filtered several times through Corning fine glass filters (10 microns) in order to free it of extraneous dust particles which might cause considerable error due to additional scattering. A definite volume of TiO_2 sol was used. The concentration of the coagulating electrolyte (KNO_3) was so adjusted that the rate of aggregation was slow. The final concentration of the electrolyte in the mixture was maintained constant, viz., 7.6×10^{-3} (N). Different volumes of pure ethanol were used in order to vary the dielectric constant of the medium. Molecular ratios of ethanol: water, thus prepared, were 0.139, 0.199, 0.321, and 0.427. The dielectric constants of the respective solutions were found to be 61.0, 58.5, 51.5, and 46.0.

Turbidity measurements of the above mixtures at certain intervals of time were carried out in the Brice-Phoenix Universal Light Scattering Photometer and all measurements were taken at 25°. For the present investigation, light of wave length 546 m μ was selected as very little of it was absorbed by TiO_2 sol in $H_2O/EtOH$ medium. That the particles of the sol were spherical in shape was ascertained by a separate study by light scattering and electron microscopy. The average radius of the particles was found to be 6.25×10^{-6} cm.

The measurement of turbidity was started shortly after mixing the sol with the electrolyte. Fig. 1 represents how turbidity changes with time in different mixtures. It is evident from these curves that the time required to attain an equiturbidity point is different for different mixtures.

FIG. 1

DISCUSSION

Considering the double-layer interaction theory of Verwey and Overbeek⁴, the following expression for the stability ratio (W) follows from an approximate evaluation of the integral,

$$W = 2 \int_0^{\infty} \frac{v}{e} \frac{1}{\kappa r} \cdot dS/S^2$$

as obtained by Recrink from the consideration that $e^{v/KT}$ has a sharp maximum when plotted as a function of S , so that $W \approx \frac{1}{2Kr} \cdot e^{v_{\max} \cdot K/T}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \log W = & - \left(\frac{0.85 \times 10^{-6} \times r \gamma^2}{KT v^2} + \frac{1}{2} \right) \log C v^2 \\ & - \left(\frac{1.70 \times 10^{-6} \times r \gamma^2}{KT v^2} \right) \log \frac{4.9 \times 10^4 v^2 A}{\gamma^2} \\ & - \left(\frac{0.85 \times 10^{-6} \times r \gamma^2}{KT v^2} + \frac{1}{2} \right) \log \frac{8 \pi e^2 N_{\Delta v}}{DKT} - \log 2r \quad \dots \quad (1) \end{aligned}$$

where C is expressed in mM/litre, r is the radius of the spherical particles, A is the attraction const., and

$$\gamma = \frac{e^{Z^2} - 1}{e^{Z^2} + 1}$$

with $Z = v e \psi_0 / KT$ and other symbols have their usual significance.

As ethanol is added to the colloid-electrolyte mixture, it is preferable to replace concentration terms (C) by activity (a). All the quantities in the right hand side of the equation (1), except D and (a) may be taken to be constant. Therefore W may be expressed as $\log W \propto -\log(a/D)$ or

$$W \propto \log(D/a) \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

Again, the stability ratio, W , can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} W &= \frac{\text{time required for slow coagulation}}{\text{time required for rapid coagulation}} \\ &= t/T. \end{aligned}$$

Now, as T is constant for a given sol, so W can be related to the experimentally measured time (t) for the attainment of the same turbidity in media of different dielectric constants, so that for the same hypothetical standard rate of rapid coagulation,

$$\log W \propto \log t \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Combining expressions (2) and (3), we have

$$\log t \propto \log(D/a) \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

From Fig. 1, it is evident that as the molecular ratio of ethanol to water increases, i.e., as the dielectric constant of the medium decreases, the time, t , taken to attain a particular turbidity, becomes smaller. From Fig. 1 it can be shown that the intervals of time required to attain a particular turbidity (0.2) for different mixtures having dielectric constants 61.0, 58.5, 51.5, and 46.0 are 61.5, 46.0, 25.0, and 10.5 minutes respectively. Again, the intervals of time required to attain another turbidity value (0.3) for the above mixtures are 107.5, 74.0, 41.0, and 17.0 respectively. Activity coefficients, and hence the acti-

vities of the respective solutions having different dielectric constants, have been calculated by using Debye-Hückel's equation:

$$-\log f_i = \frac{0.434 e^2}{2DKT} \sqrt{\frac{1}{DT}} \cdot Z_i^2 \sqrt{\sum m_i Z_i^2}$$

Fig. 2 indicates that linear relationships are obtained when $\log(D/a)$ is plotted against $\log t$. This is in agreement with expression (4).

From Sorum's data on the coagulation of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol in a given time, t , in presence of different amounts of EtOH, we have plotted $\log D$ against $\log a$ (a being activity of the added electrolyte). In Fig. 3, curves I, II and III refer to $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sols of different concentrations, viz., 2.0 g., 4.0 g., and 8.0 g. Fe_2O_3 /litre respectively. Since in Sorum's experiment t is kept constant, it is expected from expression (4) that plot of $\log D$ against $\log a$ should be linear and it may be observed from Fig. 3 that this is actually so. It may be noticed, however, that one of the points (marked A) of the concentrated sol (curve III, Fig. 3) falls appreciably below the straight line.

From Fig. 2, it is to be noticed that the experimentally determined slope of $\log t / \log(D/a)$ curve has the value 9.0, whereas the theoretical slope, calculated from equation (1) by taking $\psi_0 = \zeta = 30.9\text{mV}^*$ is 11.1. The agreement may be considered fairly satisfactory in view of the various approximations involved.

DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA-9.

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*Generally $\psi_0 = \zeta$ ($\zeta < \psi_0$); since ψ_0 cannot be obtained experimentally, we assumed for the present case $\psi_0 = \zeta$ (obtained from electrokinetic experiments). It has been shown⁸ that at low surface charge densities ψ_0 indeed approaches ζ .